

Informed consent for the patients involved in the study of HIV/AIDS infection (Kilombero&Ulanga Antiretroviral Cohort (KIULARCO))

Dear Sir/Madam,

The Chronic Diseases Clinic (CDCI) of Ifakara is a clinic for people living with HIV. Since 2004, the Ifakara Health Institute (IHI) collects anonymized data from patients of CDCI with the aim to better understand their needs and to improve services for HIV-infected persons.

We ask you for participation in this ongoing study. Whether you will agree to participate or not, you will be treated equally according the National guidelines and your current needs.

Today we would like to tell you about our work and your rights relating to your participation in this project. We would like you to read the information in this paper and sign at the end if you agree with us to participate in this project. If you cannot read, a member of our team will read it to you and answer your questions.

In summary,

Information on different aspects of an infection with HIV is very important, since it leads to **better understanding of the disease** as well as different treatment regimens. In rural areas of Sub-saharan Africa, there is still little information about patients infected with the HIV virus. The purpose of this research is to generate knowledge that will lead to better understanding of HIV/AIDS epidemic in order to improve the outcomes of HIV infected patients living in either Kilombero, Ulanga or Bagamoyo districts, but also in other parts of Africa.

Participants are patients infected with HIV who agree to participate. Adults aged **at least 18 years sign a consent**, for those who are aged under 18 years we will ask their **caregiver** to sign the informed consent on their behalf. Additionally, those aged 10-18 years are asked to sign and those becoming 18 years of age while being in the cohort.

During your routine visits at the clinics, we will **collect information** on your health status, on the medication you are taking and on the laboratory results. Also, we are interested on other diseases that might affect your wellbeing, such as arterial hypertension or co-infections. Additionally, we will record different demographic information, economic and social factors that can be associated with HIV infection.

All this information will be stored with **high confidentiality**. For analysis, anonymized data will be extracted from the local database. Results serve to improve knowledge about the HIV epidemic and aim at improved outcomes of HIV-infected patients. Furthermore, **blood and other biological samples** obtained from patients for routine analyses during medical consultations will be stored in our laboratory at IHI for research on HIV/AIDS and other associated comorbidities.

The **duration of the study** is indeterminate. Blood samples may be stored for an indeterminate time

Principles of our Research

If you decide to participate in Kilombero and Ulanga Antiretroviral Cohort, we will collect the following information from you:

- Your current health status, symptoms that might indicate an opportunistic infection such as tuberculosis or another disease requiring treatment. Information on drug intake, social factors affecting treatment outcome including perceived stigma and depression symptoms
- Physical and mental status examination and vital signs such as blood pressure and body weight

Laboratory results including CD4 cell count, safety laboratory, screening for co-infections and co-morbidities and viral load.

- Information on the type of antiretroviral treatment you are receiving and side effects (if any) after starting treatment as well as other drugs prescribed.
- If you are pregnant and give birth, we collect data on the health of your infant until the age of 24 months

Since all the above-mentioned information will be usually collected after every six months, you will be seen by a doctor during these visits.

Also, yearly a total of 10 ml of blood will be drawn for different laboratory investigations. Most of these investigations will be focused on the outcome of HIV-infection and of clinically relevant other diseases. Both samples and results will be kept with very high confidentiality in our laboratory at IHI.

Advantages

All the information obtained from this project will be analyzed and used to improve treatment and care among HIV patients. In addition, the results obtained from this project will also be used for designing other projects for finding new drugs to treat HIV/AIDS. Your participation in this project will help to improve treatment and care for all HIV-infected patients, including yourself.

Disadvantages

If you agree to participate, after every 12 months additional 10ml of blood will be drawn during the same blood withdrawal as per routine. Your participation will not hinder you from having additional investigations provided by other health facilities (not in our project) or surgical procedures if needed. Your participation will be voluntarily; you will not receive any compensation from our project.

Results

Our health experts will be informing you on different research results obtained during the whole time of this project. Participation in this project is entirely voluntary. You can decide to stop participating in this project at any time and this will not affect your future treatment and care. Not participating in this project does not mean you will not receive your antiretroviral treatment.

Privacy and Data Security

All data will be collected and stored using the ID number from the National AIDS Control program. These numbers will be known only by medical professionals and will be used to compare your laboratory results with your demographic and clinical characteristics. Results from analyses will be discussed by the scientific board consisting of scientists experienced in HIV treatment and care from Ifakara Health Institute. All the information we collect from you will be kept with very high confidentiality from the beginning of your participation to the end. You will have a right to look at all information, that has been collected from you. In case you have any question related to your participation in our project, please do not hesitate to discuss with your treating doctor or you can contact:

Prof Dr. Maja Weisser, Head of Research of CDCI (+255 621 029 569)

Dr. Herry Mapesi, Principal investigator of KIULARCO (+255 627 633 400)

Dr. Robert Ndege, Head of CDCI (+255 715 536 822)

Dr. Ezekiel Luoga, Deputy Head of CDCI (+255 657 490 784)

Please read this consent form very carefully.

Please ask if there is anything you do not understand and you need additional information.

Information on acceptance

- I have spoken to the Medical experts / coordinator of this project and they have provided me with a written document on the purpose, the logistics, the advantages and disadvantages of participating in this project.
- I have read and understood the patients' information from 01.09.2017. (If I cannot read, a dedicated healthcare person has read the content to me). All the questions I asked about my participation in this project have been answered with clarity and completeness.
- I received a copy of my informed consent form for my participation in this project.
- I have had enough time to make the decision to participate in this project and I have sufficient knowledge about this project.
- My participation in the project is entirely my voluntary decision. I can decide to stop participating in this project at any time without giving any reason to anyone and this will not affect my treatment in the future.
- I have agreed to participate in this project, all the information that I will provide will be protected and will only be available for relevant authorities as well as the board of ethics or scientists in this project. All this information will be treated with confidentiality during the whole time of my participation in this project.

Place / Date	Patient (First and surname)	Signature of patient
Place / Date	Patient's caregiver* (First and surname)	Signature of the caregiver (if the patient is younger than 18 years)
Place / Date	Doctor (First and surname)	Signature of the doctor
*Specify the relationship between the caregiver and the patient		

Ifakara, 15.11.2020